

PRELIMINARY DETERMINATION OF GEOTHERMAL POTENTIAL AREA USING REMOTE SENSING; CASE STUDY IN RAJABASA VOLCANO COMPLEX, SOUTH LAMPUNG DISTRICT, LAMPUNG PROVINCE

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ABSTRACT

National energy needs are still dependent on fossil fuels, but are inversely proportional to the depletion of reserves. Therefore, economical and environmentally friendly renewable energy is needed to meet these needs, one of which is geothermal energy. Geothermal energy is heat energy stored in rocks below surface with a fluid content inside. One of geothermal potential areas that needs to be developed is in Rajabasa Volcano Complex. This is evidenced by presence of geothermal manifestations on surface in form of fumaroles, hot springs, and hot mud pools. These manifestations are controlled by Sumatran Fault System which is indicated as a pathway for fluid migration. The research method used is a remote sensing technique using Landsat 8 OLI. Results from remote sensing can be used as a guide for further exploration. This method is considered efficient because it can describe the manifestations of geothermal surfaces without direct field observation. This research aims to identify the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Land Surface Temperature (LST), map the geological structure, and predict the geothermal potential area. LST analysis shows the highest value mostly in the south of the research area with a value of 31.759°C. It has good correlation with the NDVI results, which the lowest value is in the south of research location with value of 0.216. Interpretation of geological structures as identification of lineament to determine direction of heat sources associated with process of hydrothermal change. It can be concluded that the very high potential area of geothermal in the Rajabasa Volcano Complex is at coordinate x: 571076-573623 and y: 9358642-935532 with an area of 684.936 hectares is correlated with presence of hot spring, fumarole, and warm ground manifestations in the research area. Thus, it can be one of references in follow-up to the development of geothermal exploration

Keywords: Geothermal, Landsat 8, Rajabasa, Remote Sensing

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the availability of conventional energy has decreased continuously resulting in the need for alternative energy development. One promising alternative energy to be developed to replace conventional energy needs is geothermal energy. Geothermal energy is heat energy stored in rocks below the surface with a fluid content in it. This energy is considered to be more environmentally friendly, economical, and safe because it does not require large space for exploration and exploitation. In addition, geothermal energy plays a role as a renewable natural resource with great potential to support national development. According to the Pusat Sumberdaya Geologi (2017), the potential of geothermal energy in Indonesia is 28.5 GWe. One of which is located in the Rajabasa Volcano Complex, South Lampung District, Lampung Province. Geologically, the Rajabasa Volcano complex is in the volcanic arc zone of Sumatra Island. According to Bronto et al., (2012), Rajabasa Volcano was formed by pre-Rajabasa volcanic cone reconstruction. Knowing that there is a potential for geothermal energy requires further investigation to exploration and exploitation the area. At present, in geothermal studies remote sensing techniques are considered to have high, efficient, and low cost observation accuracy because they do not come into contact with objects, areas, and phenomena that are being investigated. This remote sensing method is not only used for exploration, but also in exploitation to monitor geothermal working areas (Bromley et al., 2015). Remote sensing uses the Landsat 8 OLI satellite image (Operational Land Imager) can identify hot spots based on optional sensors as Thermal Infrared Sensors (TIRS) to produce data continuity with resolutions up to 30 m. The Landsat 8 band combination provides the multispectral color shape that is owned. According to Sitanggang (2010), Landsat 8 can be used to determine geothermal locations, monitor ecosystems, natural resource management, land use mapping, and disaster mitigation. This study aims to identify the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Land Surface Temperature (LST),

map the geological structure, and predict the geothermal prospect area as a first step reference in planning geothermal exploration in the Rajabasa Volcano Complex area.

REGIONAL GEOLOGY

The research area is at the southern tip of Sumatra Island, precisely in the Rajabasa Volcano Complex, South Lampung District, Lampung Province.

Stratigraphy Regional

Stratigraphically, the Rajabasa Volcano Complex consists of Tangkil, Pematang Park, Balerang, and Mount Rajabasa. According to Suswati et.al. (2001), volcanic products from the Rajabasa Volcano Complex are divided into five periods from old to young, namely (1) Tua Tangkil Volcanic Products, consisting of Tua Tangkil (Tv) Volcanic Product Units that are Pliocene aged, (2) Tua Pematang Taman Volcanic Products, consisting of a Pleistocene Tua Pematang Taman Product Unit (PTv), (3) Balerang Volcano Products, consisting of a Balerang (BI) Pyroclastic Unit and a Pleistocene Lava Balerang (Ba) Unit, (4) Eruption Product Samping Bukit 845, consisting of Lava 845 (845I) units in Pleistocene age (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Stratigraphy of Rajabasa Volcano Complex (Suswati et.al., 2001)

Based on the Geological Map of Tanjungkarang Sheet (Mangga et al., 1993), in the study area there

were three volcanic rock units of varying ages, from Tertiary to Quaternary, Andesite Unit (Tpv), Lampung Formation (QTI), and Rajabasa Volcanic Rock (Qhv) (Figure 2). The Andesite Unit composed of andesitic lava as a product of tertiary volcanism spread westward to the southeastern part of the Rajabasa Volcano. The Lampung Formation consists of riolytic tuffs, pumice tuffs, clay, and tuff sandstone. Rajabasa Volcanic rock belongs to the young volcanic deposits (quaternary) consisting of basaltic-andesitic lava, breccias, and tuffs forming the body of the Rajabasa volcanic cone (Table 1). Rock composition indicates that Rajabasa Volcano is a composite type or Strato cone. According to Bronto et.al. (2012), based on the characteristics of the current lava flows on Mount Rajabasa, this Andesite Unit is predicted to have grown not far from the source of the eruption. The history of eruptions in Rajabasa Volcano was recorded by Van Padang (1951) in (Budiarjo et al, 1995) who said that in 1863 and 1892 there was an increase in volcanic activity, but no eruption had occurred.

Table 1: Stratigraphy of Rajabasa Volcano Complex with description (Modified from Mangga et al., 1993)

Age	Rock Unit Name	Description
Quaternary	Rajabasa Volcanic Rocks (Qhv)	Lava (andesite-basalt), breccias, tuff, spread out locally in the Rajabasa Volcano, southern part of Kalianda City.
Quaternary-Tertiary	Lampung Formation (QTI). Previous name Lampung Tuff (van Bemmelen, 1949)	Pumiceous tuff, rhyolitic tuff, tuffite, welded tuff, tuffaceous claystone, tuffaceous sandstone, distributed widely from Bakauheni to northern Kalianda till northern part of Bandar Lampung City. Pumiceous tuff, yellowish grey-greyish white, medium- to coarse-grained, poorly sorted, mainly comprising pumice and rock fragments. Rhyolitic tuff, brownish white, slightly jointed, hard. Tuffaceous sandstone, yellowish broken white, subrounded, partly pumiceous, somewhat soft, often shows cross bed structure, generally of dacitic composition.
Tertiary	Andesite (Tpv)	Andesitic lava, light-dark grey, hard, porphyritic; plagioclase, amphibole, and pyroxene phenocrysts embedded in aphanitic groundmass; outcrop relatively fresh, strongly/sheeting jointed; cropping out in the eastern part of Rajabasa Volcano; unconformably overlain by the Lampung Formation.

Figure 2: Geological map of Rajabasa Volcano Complex (modification from Mangga et.al., 1993)

Tectonic Regional

The island of Sumatra located in the southwest of the Sundaland continent and the subduction lane between the Indo-Australian Plate that subducted into the Eurasian Plate. The subduction of the plate produces subduction that occurs along the Sunda Trench and the movement of dextral strike-slip fault of the Sumatran Fault. (Figure 3). Sumatra Island is a collision product of microcontinent in the end of Pre-Tertiary (Barber et al., 2005). According to Van Bemmelen (1934) in Nazarwin, (1994) Sumatra Island consists of four physiographic zones, namely the Lowland Zone, the Highland Zone, the Hills Zone, and the Mountain Zone. This research area belongs to the Mountain Zone. Based on the geological map of Tanjung Karang (Mangga et al., 1994), the lineament and fault structure trending NW-SE and N-S. The structural pattern trending NW-SE is an extension pattern from Sumatran Fault System. The fault pattern trending N-S is indicated as a basement structure pattern commonly found in the Java sea (Martodjojo, 2003).

Quaternary volcanoes along the Sunda and Banda arc of Indonesia is a famous example of subduction-related volcanism. The Sunda Strait located in the southeastern part of Sumatra island marks the transition region from orthogonal to oblique subduction and interpreted as an extension area and as the result of a northwestward motion of the arc slices located between the trench and the Sumatran Fault System (Barber et al., 2005). According to Ninkovich (1976) in Barber et al. (2005) the opening of the Sunda Strait is the result of a Sumatra clockwise rotation of around 20 ° around the axis located near the Sunda Strait since the Late Miocene. South Lampung is divided into three blocks, namely Bengkulu Block, Central Block, and Sekampung Block (Van Bemmelen, 1934 in Nazarwin 1994). The Bengkulu and Central Block blocks are separated by Semangko Fault while the Central Block and Sekampung Block are separated by Lampung Fault. This Lampung fault continues to the south and cuts off the Rajabasa Mountain complex and Mount Balerang. The Lampung fault has a northwest-southeast direction and local faults that are northeast-southwest. Lampung Fault is a strike-slip fault and predicted controlling the geothermal system in the north and southeast of Mount Rajabasa (Amin, 1988 in Nazarwin, 1994). In addition to faults, other geological structures that developed is a crater which also acts as a geothermal controller. The crater is the Balerang Crater which is located on the summit of Mount Balerang and the Rajabasa Peak Crater which is located at the top of Rajabasa Volcano. The Rajabasa Peak Crater and the Balerang Peak Crater formed steep slope around the crater. These slopes is a product of an eruption followed by destruction phase along with the process of forming the crater morphology in Mount Rajabasa (Suswati, et al., 2001).

Figure 3: Tectonic setting regional of Sumatra Island (Barber et al., 2005)

METHODS

In general, the research method uses remote sensing with Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager (OLI) and secondary data (Figure 4). The acquisition of Landsat data used consisted of the last 4 months, that is September, October, November and December 2018 which focused on the SWIRS and NIR bands (4,5,7,10) and 11 bands to find out the probability of geothermal potential obtained and predict potential in the future. This data was obtained on the USGS earthexplorer page and then selecting the Rajabasa area, South Lampung. Processing is supported by GIS software, ArcGIS 10.5 and Envi to make image corrections, band ratios, and composite bands. From the results of this processing, it will get information about NDVI (The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) or the level of vegetation density and LST (Land Surface Temperature) or soil surface temperature, and Land Surface Emissivity (LSE). Then, RBI data from South Lampung was used with a scale of 1:50.000, such as contours and administrative boundaries to determine the height and width in the study area. After obtaining LST and NDVI from the 4 months, calculated the mean, so that the value of LST and NDVI can be obtained as a reference in determining the potential zoning of geothermal energy. Then, an overlay with RBI data is carried out, so that the geothermal potential map can be obtained which contains the level of geothermal potential. Furthermore, to interpret the geological structure data related to hydrothermal migration using Digital Elevation Model (DEM) data. After knowing the regions that have geothermal prospects, an overlay with lineament data and secondary data in the form of geothermal manifestations is carried out to support and delegate areas that have geothermal prospects, so that it will produce very high geothermal potential areas for further exploration.

Figure 4: The workflow of research

RESULTS

Analysis carried out using Landsat 8 OLI satellite images combined with regional geological information, the results of which can be explained. Each recorded image has different characteristics, this is caused by external factors during the data acquisition process, such as clouds, solar altitude, and climate change resulting in different surface vegetation indices and surface temperatures is September, October, November, and December 2018.

Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)

The vegetation index value is one indicator to determine the level of drought or greenness in an area. According to Saragih et al. (2015), the lower the vegetation index, the higher the geothermal potential in the area. In determining the surface value of temperature, it needs to be combined with the condition of the value of NDVI. In general, the area indicated as having a reddish-yellow hotspot indicates a slight index of vegetation around it. The results of the NDVI analysis show a value of -0.003-0,576 (Table 2). NDVI uses minimum and maximum values to get comparative values between few and many vegetations. Therefore, the NDVI value is an index value, not absolute vegetation. A little vegetation located in the southern part of the study area indicated by the NDVI value of 0.216 (Figure 5). NDVI analysis shows high vegetation density in the peak area of Rajabasa Volcano, while low density is in the middle to the foot of the mountain. The high density at the top of Rajabasa Volcano is interpreted as part of the Barisan Mountain National Park forest area, while the low vegetation area is being indicated as an area of rice fields, plantations and settlements.

Figure 5: The result of NDVI in Rajabasa Volcano Complex (A) September, (B) October, (C) November, and (D) December.

Table 2: The range value of NDVI

Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)		
Month	Min	Max
September	-0.047249	0.514063
October	-0.110975	0.576505
November	-0.003416	0.216015
December	-0.080653	0.529236

Land Surface Temperature (LST)

According to Zhang et.al. (2012), the higher the surface temperature, the higher the geothermal potential in the area. The highest hotspots usually

occur in areas that have a relatively low altitude and are close to the lineament zone or geological structure. However, the value of air density will decrease and be linear with air temperature in areas that have high elevation, such as hills and mountains (Hazred et.al., 2018). Volcanic activity and the movement of the Semangko Fault in the Rajabasa Volcano Complex and its surroundings have caused magma activity to be active, resulting in several heat sources on the surface. Based on LST analysis, regions that have geothermal manifestations are located on the slopes of the foot of the Rajabasa Volcano with a high temperature value of -4.57167°C - 31.7596°C . The availability of existing manifestations is controlled by the Sumatran Fault System as a fluid migration path. The results of the surface temperature recorded and calculated resulted in temperatures ranging from -40.0611°C - 31.7596°C (Table 3). Based on the results of the fourth thermal band, September has a higher temperature than others. This is because September is a wet month, so it contains a lot of surface water and absorbs more sunlight. In November anomalies were found which showed very low temperature values compared to the others. This occurs because of image recording and conversion factors when modeling LST maps (Figure 6).

Figure 6: The result of LST in Rajabasa Volcano Complex (A) September, (B) October, (C) November, and (D) December.

Table 3: The range value of LST

Land Surface Temperature (LST)		
Month	Min ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Max ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
September	-10.3413	31.7596
October	-9.96573	22.3932
November	-40.0611	-4.57167
December	-9.96567	22.3932

The temperature distribution on the histogram in September, October and December forms a curved shape, like a bell. This form shows the distribution of surface temperature in the study area is relatively normal, whereas in November it formed a fluctuating up and down curve which showed significant continuous temperature changes around it (Figure 7).

Figure 7: The histogram of LST in Rajabasa Volcano Complex (A) September, (B) October, (C) November, and (D) December.

Based on the analysis that has been done, the existence of hotspots in the study area occurs in the weak zone located along the line of structural lineament with a low NDVI value, where the vegetation does not develop in the zone of hydrothermal change.

Fault and Fracture Density (FFD)

The presence of valleys and steep slopes in the morphology of the study area shows the presence of tectonic deformations. Lineament analysis is needed by using ASTERDEM to describe the direction and style of work in the research area. Furthermore, lineament interpretations can determine the direction of the heat source associated with the hydrothermal change process. Lineament calculation is done by automatic extraction of 380 lineament. Lineament data is processed into a rose diagram to analyze the direction of lineament. The results of lineament interpretation shows that the main trend is developing in the study area, that is W-E and N-S (Figure 8). The main trend is formed by secondary structures, while the regional trend of the Sumatran Fault System with NW-SE direction acts as the primary structure. However, a small portion of lineament was found trending NW-SE in harmony with the primary structure. The direction that develops acts as a pathway for fluid migration both from the subsurface, to the surface, and vice versa. Thus, the main trend trending NE-SW is interpreted as a secondary structure produced by the movement of the primary structure.

Figure 8: The lineament rose diagram of Rajabasa Volcano Complex

After that, lineament data associated with existing structures in the area is used to make a FFD map. Based on the calculation of density values using the FFD method, the Rajabasa Volcano Complex area is grouped into three density classes, namely low density (0-1.1 km/km²) which is shown in dark green-moss green, medium density (1.1-2.2 km/km²) with light green-young orange, and high density (2.2-3.3 km/km²) indicated by orange-red color (Figure 9). High density values are in several regions, namely around Mount Belirang and in the north and northeast of Rajabasa Volcano. This area is indicated by a black oval line. In contrast, in the western and eastern parts of Rajabasa Volcano and the western part of Mount Belirang it has a low density zone, so that geothermal manifestations are very difficult to find or far from geothermal sources.

Figure 9: The Fault and Fracture Density (FFD) map of Rajabasa Volcano Complex

Geothermal Potential Area

Determination of potential geothermal areas using the overlay index method with parameters including vegetation index, surface temperature, surface manifestations, Fault and Fracture Density (FFD) analysis, and secondary data in the form of field observations from previous researchers.

The presence of surface geothermal manifestations analyzed using NDVI shows that the area around the southern part of the Rajabasa Volcano has a low value of 0.216°C (Figure 5). Surface temperatures that are interpreted using Infrared Thermal Sensors have a good correlation with the NDVI results, where the highest values are mostly in the southern part of the study area with a value of 31.759°C (Figure 6). The results of lineament patterns that have been manually analyzed using ASTERDEM show the main trend with W-E and N-S trending (Figure 8). This pattern is included as a secondary structure that is part of the primary structure of the Sumatran Fault System. Based on FFD method, high

density values are in several regions, namely around Mount Belirang and in the north and northeast of Rajabasa Volcano (Figure 9). After NDVI analysis, LST, lineament, and FFD, then overlaid to produce a new potential geothermal area. The area identified as having high geothermal potential is in the northeast, east, and south of the study area. Research conducted by Darmawan et al. (2015) and Hafiz et.al. (2018), found 15 geothermal manifestations such as hot spring, fumarole and warm ground in the Rajabasa Volcano Complex.

The locations of manifestations found by Darmawan et al. (2015) and Hafiz et.al. (2018) were then overlaid with geothermal zoning maps that have been made. Based on remote sensing analysis using Landsat 8 OLI. The overlay results from geothermal potential zonation maps and field observations from previous researchers indicate that the geothermal prospect area of the Rajabasa Volcano Complex is located at coordinates x: 571076-573623 and y: 9358642-935532 with an area of 684,936 hectares

(Figure 10). However, direct field observations are needed to validate the presence of geothermal manifestations as a further step in geothermal exploration. Thus, the use of remote sensing satellite imagery can be used as a preliminary survey to identify the presence of hot anomalies from hotspots.

Figure 10: Geothermal potential map of Rajabasa Volcano Complex with overlay distribution geothermal manifestations from study previous

CONCLUSION

Remote sensing is an effective method for identifying heat sources for the initial stages in geothermal exploration. From the NDVI analysis method, LST, lineament analysis, and secondary data can interpret possible geothermal potential areas based on the overlay method. NDVI analysis shows a value of -0.003-0,576, where the vegetation is slightly in the southern part of the research area indicated by the NDVI value of 0.216. This has a good correlation with the results of LST, where the highest temperature is in the southern slope of the foot of the Rajabasa Volcano with a value of 31.759°C. The results of the lineament analysis using ASTERDEM show the direction of the main trend in the W-E and N-S trending study area. The pattern is interpreted as a secondary structure produced by the movement of the primary structure, namely the Sumatran Fault System with the NW-SE direction. The very high prospect area of the geothermal area of Rajabasa Volcanic Complex lies in the coordinates x: 571076-573623 and y: 9358642-935532 with an area of 684,936 hectares. This is supported by the location of geothermal manifestations in the form of hot spring, fumarole, and warm ground in the research area. However, there is a need for direct field observations to

validate the existence of geothermal manifestations from the results of spatial analysis that has been carried out as a further step in geothermal exploration. It is necessary to develop geothermal point determination methods using satellite imagery that has a higher resolution and less noise, so that the results given are more accurate and can be a reference in the early stages of geothermal exploration.

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